

INSTITUTO POLITÉCNICO DE SANTARÉM

**POLITÉCNICO
DE SANTARÉM**

Revisão de Literatura

Manual de Apoio

[mestrado Recursos Digitais em Educação | Escola Superior de Educação]

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Ana Loureiro | Professora Adjunta

[Ciência ID 9E13-E4A0-3ABE](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1322-3070)

[ORCID iD 0000-0003-1322-3070](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1322-3070)

O que vamos explorar neste manual:

- Definição do conceito de revisão de escopo;
- Porquê recorrer a uma revisão de escopo;
- Evolução da revisão de escopo;
- Framework metodológica de 6 etapas;
- Como começar;
- Definição de cada etapa;
- Aspetos práticos de aplicação.

Revisão de escopo ou “scoping review”

- Comumente utilizado na área da saúde;
- Aplicável no contexto de investigação em educação.

Método para rapidamente “*reviewing literature which has not yet been comprehensively reviewed*” (Peters *et al.*, p. 141)

Objetivam mapear rapidamente os principais conceitos que sustentam uma área de pesquisa. (Arksey e O’Malley, 2005)

Ajudam a determinar se se justifica uma revisão sistemática da literatura.

Revisão de escopo - definição

As definições referem-se geralmente ao ‘*mapeamento*’, um processo de resumo de uma série de evidências a fim de *transmitir a amplitude e profundidade* de um campo ou área de estudo.

As revisões de escopo diferem das revisões sistemáticas porque, tipicamente, os autores *não avaliam a qualidade* dos estudos incluídos.

Também diferem das revisões narrativas ou de literatura na medida em que o processo de delimitação do escopo *exige uma reinterpretação analítica* da literatura.

[\[Levac, Colquhoun & O’Brien, 2010\]](#)

Porquê recorrer a uma revisão de escopo

	Revisão Sistemática	Revisão de Escopo
Investigação	Focalizada	Frequentemente ampla / exploratória
CrITÉrios de inclusão/exclusão	Definidos <i>a priori</i>	Flexíveis, podem ser alterados <i>post hoc</i>
Qualidade	Filtros de qualidade aplicados	Não é uma prioridade inicial
Síntese	Tipicamente quantitativo	Tipicamente qualitativo
Objetivo	Extração detalhada de dados “knowledge accumulation”	Identifica padrões e lacunas na literatura “mapping knowledge”
Questão típica	“qual é a eficiência de... comparado com... em xxx estudantes”	“o que é conhecido sobre xxx na literatura”

Adaptado de: Davidson, G. (30/07/2019). *How to do a Scoping Review?* [Video file]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=skMBA5Dlono>

Evolução da revisão de escopo

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Framework metodológica de 6 etapas

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Como começar?

- Construir um protocolo de intenções de investigação;
- reconhecer as "suas" limitações e descrever os desvios;
 - os desvios são actividades planeadas que diferem do que é recomendado;
 - não cumprimento do protocolo descrito a posteriori.

1. definir a questão de investigação

Protocol	Variances?
1.1 Clearly define the research question by combining a broad question with a specific context of enquiry	<i>Unlikely</i>
1.2 Consider the rationale for conducting the study before specifying and commenting on the purpose of the study	
1.3 Stipulate the outputs of the study	
1.4 Review and consider refining the research question including the terms within it, after the piloting process, identification of relevant studies and study selection	

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2. encontrar artigos relevantes

	Protocol	Variances?
2.1	Seek advice and guidance from the subject librarian	<i>Experience</i>
2.2	State the lead researcher's prior experience of using scoping review methodology, the limitations associated and how these can be overcome.	<i>Grey literature</i>
2.3	Complete a piloting exercise: run searches on the primary database, then modify search strategy; finalise the pilot search strategy; review and select relevant articles.	<i>Hand searching</i>
2.4	Consider modifying the search strategy and research question after greater knowledge of the literature is acquired. If limiting the scope, justify reasons for this and acknowledge potential limitations.	
2.5	Run the final version of the search on the primary database, then run on other selected databases (adjusted)	
2.6	Search the internet for articles accessed through relevant networks and organisations. Include any articles known to researcher. Consider identification through hand-searching relevant journals and reference lists of relevant articles. Consider sourcing grey literature.	
2.7	Import all articles into a reference manager. Exclude duplicates.	

Dr Gail Davison gdavison05@qub.ac.uk

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3. seleccionar os estudos

	Protocol	Variances
3.1	Decide on inclusion and exclusion criteria at initial meeting with supervisor. Consider setting a deadline after which no more studies would be included. Consider using 2 reviewers.	<i>2nd reviewer</i>
3.2	Acknowledge iterative nature: review inclusion/exclusion criteria; refine plan for selection of further articles; refine research question	<i>Deadline setting</i>
3.3	Meet with supervisor to review research question, search strategy and criteria during and after all articles reviewed for selection	<i>Meet with other researcher</i>
3.4	If inclusion of an article is questionable, review with supervisor. If disagreement arises, request a third reviewer's opinion.	
3.5	Present article selection on a PRISMA diagram	

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4. traçar os dados

	Protocol	Variances?
4.1	Construct a 'Data charting form' with advice from the project supervisor. Consider using 2 reviewers to extract data.	2 nd reviewer
4.2	Review after piloting on 10 studies and determine whether extracted variables can answer the research question, aims and objectives; modify the form if required	
4.3	Complete the Data Charting on each study	

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5. recolher, analisar e apresentar os resultados

	Protocol	Variances?
5.1	Stage 1 Analysis: Complete basic numerical analysis, to show the extent, nature and distribution of studies. Complete qualitative content analysis (if appropriate)	-
5.2	Stage 2 Reporting: Report the results, and produce the outcome that refers to the overall research question, aims and objectives	-
5.3	Stage 3 Consider: Consider the meaning of these findings, as they relate to the overall purpose of the study; implications for future research, practice, policy	-

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6. exercício de consulta | consolidação (nem sempre incluído)

- 6.1 - Establish the purpose of the consultation
- 6.2 - Compile preliminary findings to be used as a foundation to inform on the context in the consultation
- 6.3 - Articulate the type of stakeholders to consult
- 6.4 - Outline how data is to be collected, analysed, reported and integrated
- 6.5 - Consider incorporating opportunities for knowledge transfer and exchange
- 6.6 - Complete the consultation exercise and analysis

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Exemplo prático de aplicação

[Imwa, M. (2020). *The potential of using smartphone in teaching and learning in Secondary school – A Descriptive study of selected schools in Maputo City*. Dissertação de Mestrado. Universidade Aberta. <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.2/10094>]

Método “scoping review” - como aplicar

- Definição de critérios de pesquisa de acordo com os **objetivos** da investigação
- Definição de **frases** específicas
- Definição de **palavras-chave**
- Definição das **bases de dados** de pesquisa
- Definição **critérios de seleção** ou de **inclusão / exclusão** (ano, língua, relevância, acesso aberto, peer-reviewed...)
- **Pesquisa**, recolha, seleção

No.	Phrase	Keywords
1.	Teachers' and students' perceptions over the use of mobile/smartphones in teaching and learning?	Teacher, perceptions, mobile-phone, Smartphone, teaching, learning
2.	Constructivist Theory and Mobile/smartphones	Learning theory, mobile/smartphones, constructivist theory
3.	Education Policy on ICT's Integration in Mozambican Schools	ICT's Policy, Education, Mozambique
4	Potential uses of smartphones in the teaching and learning process	uses, Smartphone, teaching-process, education
5	Potential challenges in using mobile/smartphones in teaching and learning	Challenges, disadvantages, Smartphone, teaching, learning

Frases de pesquisa e respetivas palavras-chave

Topic 1: Teacher perceptions on the use of mobile/smartphone in teaching process			
Keywords: Teacher, perceptions, mobile-phone, smartphone, teaching, learning			
Papers	DB1: Google Scholar	DB2: ERIC	DB3: DOAJ
Ismail, I., Azizan, S. N., & Aznan, N. (2013). Mobile Phone as Pedagogical Tools: Are Teachers Ready? <i>International Education Studies</i> , 6(3), 36-47. doi:10.5539/ies.v6n3p36	X	X	
Nawi, A., Hamzah, M. L., & Rahim, A. A. (2015). Teachers Acceptance of Mobile Learning for Teaching and Learning in Islamic Education: A Preliminary Study. <i>Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education</i> , 16(1), 184-192. doi:10.17718/tojde.30611		X	
Apuke, O. D., & Iyendo, T. O. (2018). University students' usage of the internet resources for research and learning: Forms of access and perceptions of utility. <i>Heliyon</i> , 4(12). doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2018.e01052			X

Resultado da pesquisa

No	Questions	Key-words	DB1: Google Scholar	DB2: Eric	DB3: DOAJ	Total from the DBs
1	Students and Teachers perceptions on the use of mobile/smartphone in teaching process	Teacher, perceptions, mobile-phone, smartphone, teaching, learning	8	4	1	13
2	Constructivist theory and mobile/smartphones	Learning-theory, mobile/smartphones, constructivist theory	2	6	1	9
3	Potential uses of smartphones in teaching process	Potential, Uses, smartphone, teaching-process, education	9	8	3	20
4	Education Policy on ICT's Integration in Mozambican Schools	ICT's Policy, Education, Mozambique	3	0	0	3
5	Potential challenges in using mobile/smartphones in teaching and learning	challenges, disadvantages, smartphone, teaching, learning	6	6	1	13
Total			28	24	6	58

Resumo dos resultado da pesquisa

Articles					
Title	Year	Peer-reviewed	Type	Designation	
<i>Mind in society - the development of higher psychological processes</i>	1978	✓	Book	Cambridge, Massachusetts, Harvard University Press	
<i>Constructivist Learning Theory</i>	1991	✓	Conference article	CECA (International Committee of Museum Educators) Conference - Pearson, Boston	
<i>Learning theories: an educational perspective (6th Edition)</i>	2012	✓	Book	Pearson, Boston	
<i>An Epistemological Glance At The Constructivist Approach: Constructivist Learning In Dewey, Piaget, And Montessori</i>	2012	✓	Journal Article	International Journal of Instruction	
<i>Adoption and Application of Mobile Learning in the Education Industry</i>	2013	✓	Journal Article	Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences	
<i>Textbooks and Constructivist Pedagogy in Saudi Arabian School Classrooms</i>	2014	✓	Journal Article	Journal of Curriculum and Teaching	
<i>Technology Integration and Learning Theory</i>	2015	✓	Journal Article	American International Journal of Contemporary Research	
<i>Handbook of research on educational technology integration and active learning</i>	2015	✓	Electronic Book	Information Science Reference, IGI Global	
<i>The Current Perspectives, Theories and Practices of Mobile Learning</i>	2016	✓	Journal Article	The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	
<i>The effects of integrating mobile devices with teaching and learning on students learning performance: A meta-analysis and research synthesis</i>	2016	✓	Journal Article	Computers & Education	
<i>Students' and Teachers' Perceptions of the Use of Mobile Technology in University Preparation Classes</i>	2017	✓	Master Thesis	Massey University, Manawatu Campus	

Metadados dos critérios de inclusão/exclusão

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